

CCE APPROACH THROUGH ABCD ANALYSIS OF 'THEORY A' ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

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Abstract:

Theory A on organizational performance challenges the existing propositions on human behaviour and motivation. It is founded in the context of changed employee mindset of the modern day employee which has undergone enormous change due to changes in technology and means of production, production relations, customer and societal perception and one's own expectations. The quest for creativity propels the employee to contribute to the organization drawing positive energy from his innate potential and tuned to best performance models around him through self-exploration. This is a management strategy which believes in delivering targets as responsibility, feeling of creativity, and contribution for motivation, identifying with the organization as commitment and accountability as a hallmark of efficiency. ABCD analysing technique refers to examining a system, model, or concept through focussing on its advantages, benefits, constraints, disadvantages by narrowing to determinant factors, key factors, and critical constituent elements. Determinant factors form the overall frame of reference while key factors represent the dimensions on which its advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages are reflected. Critical Constituent Elements (CCE) are elements which are critical to the success of the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. This paper attempts a factor and elemental analysis of Theory A using CCE approach through ABCD analysing framework.

Index Terms: Theory A, ABCD analysing framework, Theory A using ABCD Analysis, Factor & Elemental Analysis

1. Introduction:

Studying any system in nature in detail and in systematic procedure constitutes a scientific analysis of the system and such analysis leads to research on the system [1]. Studying various subsystems of a system, identifying their inter-relations, determining various variables and parameters in a system which affect the process of transforming inputs into outputs, studying the relationship between major variables to control the system performance, studying characteristics of each subsystems have importance and interest in any system focussed research [2-12]. Apart from these, while studying and analysing a system, it is essential to know the details of various factors affecting the processes of a system and hence the performance of a system so that the system can be rebuilt and improved further based on requirement. It is also possible to determine various constituent elements which decide the performance of the system. The constituent elements are those elements which decide the characteristics, features, conditions, or variables of the system in a minute or significant way. Out of many constituent elements, one can identify for a system, it is believed that some constituent elements when maintained and sustained, can have the significant impact on the function and performance of the system. Such constituent elements of a system can be called as critical constituent elements (CCE) [13].

2. About Theory A:

Recently, Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar [14-15] have developed a theory on Organizational performance for 21st century named Theory A. The essential elements of Accountability Theory (Theory A) are (1) Planning, (2) Target setting, (3) Motivation, (4) Work Strategies, (5) Responsibility, (6) Role model, (7) Monitoring & Guiding, (8)

Accountability. Theory A has been developed using following postulates which connect the above elements of organizational performance.

Postulate 1: Employee outlook has changed over time.

Postulate 2: The present day employee has considerable innate potential which the organization is looking for.

Postulate 3: His knowledge and skill could be enhanced in a conducive environment of necessity and expediency.

Postulate 4: The organization influence application of knowledge and skill into practice.

Postulate 5: Identification of role models and self exploration can transform average employee into real performer.

Postulate 6: Rewards are not only a matter of money or position, but one's own feeling of inherent creativity and contribution to the organization.

Postulate 7: Such employees are highly motivated and identifies with the organization.

Postulate 8: Targets are not externally suggested but jointly arrived at and compliance to target is out of will.

Postulate 9: Responsibility is nothing but efficiency in delivering targets to the required extent and time.

Postulate 10: Efficiency in individual and organizational performance is based on accountability to oneself, one's own job and to the job giver.

Postulate 11: Accountability is sin-qua-non to commitment. The more the commitment greater is the Accountability.

3. Theory A Implementation Procedure in an Organization:

Theory A explains a process by which managerial leadership in organizations accomplish the task through a series of steps involving the employees influencing to accomplish the desirable task efficiently [16-17]. These eight stages are provided vertically in the following table 1. The steps at each stage are provided horizontally.

Table 1: Stages of Theory A implementation Procedure [16]

S.No	Stages	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4
1	Planning	Institutional strength/weaknesses assessment	Problem identification	Joint policy formulation	Outline for action
2	Target Setting	Familiarization	Consultation	Realization	Action plan
3	Motivation	Adoption of idea	Self-exploration	Role model	Increased performance
4	Work Strategies	Individual goal setting	Team spirit	Empowerment	Providing support
5	Responsibility	Commitment	Consistency	Task execution	Target fulfilment
6	Role Model	Following example	Changing mindset	Accepting challenge	Willingness to improve
7	Monitoring	Joint review	Self appraisal	Drawing deadlines	Confirmation of accomplishment
8	Accountability	Individual commitment	Organizational influence	Creativity	Contribution

1. Planning:

- ✓ Either individually or jointly head of the organization reflects the institutional strength and weaknesses. This is a periodic function to keep the relevance of the organization updated and face newer challenges that emerge.
- ✓ As a consequence, various problems may surface, but using ingenuity and discretion, the pressing problem is zeroed in. This is collectively done.

- ✓ A candid policy is essential for backing managerial actions. This is formulated involving section heads.
- ✓ The policy spells out in clear terms the broad direction the organization will be heading for.

2. Target Setting:

- ✓ The problem that has been identified and the policy formulated has to be communicated to everyone in the organization.
- ✓ This stimulates a process of mutual consultation and dialog among members of the organization.
- ✓ As a result, the members realize what has been ailing them and how to overcome that.
- ✓ They become prepared to devote their effort towards better performance.

3. Motivation:

- ✓ Following the realization and preparedness to perform desirably, their interest is aroused through group process by which the group adopts the idea.
- ✓ This group process also helps members discover their potential through self-exploration.
- ✓ They are also influenced by their reference group namely ideal performers.
- ✓ As a result of this ideas become translated into performance.

4. Work Strategies:

- ✓ A strategy is important for success. First and foremost, it is important that the members of the organizations set their individual goals in consonance with the organizational goal. This comes in the form of a desire.
- ✓ Identical goals transform into sharing of group goals and generate team spirit.
- ✓ Materialising creative talents gives the individual a feeling of empowerment.
- ✓ The organization also extend support as an enabling strategy.

5. Responsibility:

- ✓ Assuming responsibility is owning responsibility, rather a manifestation of commitment.
- ✓ This gives speed and certainty of actions in delivering responsibility.
- ✓ Then comes task execution which is a crucial part of all.
- ✓ This is done for goal attainment that helps target fulfillment.

6. Role Model:

- ✓ Good performance is highlighted.
- ✓ Best performers become role models which influence other members in performance.
- ✓ This results in a change of attitude from somewhat positive to highly positive from the mediocre performance.
- ✓ Develops readiness to change.

7. Monitoring:

- ✓ There would be periodic re-visits to the targets set, its execution, and lack if any.
- ✓ This gives an opportunity for everyone to appraise their work/actions/task.
- ✓ As a consequence, the timeframe is set for the lag.
- ✓ Members accomplish the task.

8. Accountability:

- ✓ Individual commitment is evaluated during performance assessment. Performance is measured against group goal, individual goal, and organizational support.

- ✓ That organizational influence application of knowledge and skill into effective performance is reiterated. Performance is enhanced in a conducive environment of expediency created by necessity.
- ✓ Organization strives to foster inherent creativity to transform it and integrate it into the organizational goal.
- ✓ Acknowledgment of contribution is shared between individual and organization. Poor performers undergo recycling.

Figure 1: Organizational Assumptions Vs Managerial Assumptions in Theory A

The set of postulates pertaining to theory A could be identified as consisting of two sets of assumptions. Those which have a direct bearing on the organization in terms of employee characteristics and attributes are named as organizational assumptions while managerial assumptions refers to consequent managerial actions and results as shown in figure 1. Each organizational attribute is accompanied by a corresponding managerial action. This moves forward sequentially, resulting in a progress from task to task attainment. Goal and task are interchangeably used since goals are higher order tasks and many tasks together become a goal.

4. About ABCD Analysis Framework:

Various techniques are used to analyze the individual characteristics, system characteristics, the effectiveness of a concept or idea, the effectiveness of a strategy while studying the business value in the society. The individual characteristics or organizational effectiveness & strategies in a given environment can be studied using SWOT analysis, SWOC analysis, PEST analysis, McKinsey 7S framework, ICDT model, Portor's five force model etc. Recently introduced business analysis framework called ABCD analysis framework [18] is suitable for analysing business concepts, business systems, technology, business models or business idea in terms of determining various factors for chosen determinant issues under four constructs called advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. In the qualitative analysis using ABCD framework, the concept/system/strategy/technology/model/idea is further analysed by identifying constitutional critical factors. In the quantitative analysis using ABCD framework [13], the appropriate score/weightage is given to each constituent critical factor under each construct, through empirical research, the total score is calculated for each construct and by evaluating the scores, the concept/idea/system/technology/strategy can be

accepted or rejected. Thus ABCD analysis framework can be used as a research tool in these areas and is a simple but systematic analyzing technique for business models/systems/concepts/ideas/technology/strategy analysis [13].

5. Literature Review on ABCD Analysis:

Recently, Aithal P.S. et. al. [18] developed ABCD analyzing framework to analyze any business model/strategy/concept/system and to study its effectiveness in providing value to its stakeholders and sustainable profit through expected revenue generation. Application of ABCD analysis results in an organized list of business advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages in a systematic matrix. The entire framework is divided into various issues/area of focus and various business deployment factors affecting the business/concept can be identified and analyzed under each issue by identifying the suitable critical effective element. This analyzing technique being simple gives the guideline to identify and analyze the effectiveness of any business model, business strategy, business concept/idea, and business system. The framework is used to analyse the characteristics of "Working from Home" e-business model [19]. Based on various factors which decide the Working from Home system, a model of various factors and their constituent critical elements affecting under organizational objectives, employer point of view, employees point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived from a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compared to constraints and disadvantages of this model, so that working from home model may become more popular from the perspective of employers and employees in the organization in the future. ABCD analysis framework is used for analysing Black ocean strategy concept [20-21]. The various factors & their constituent critical factors affecting the BOS concept adopted in some of the business organizations for quick relief from the problems are identified for organizational point of view, administrative point of view, employee point of view, operational point of view, business point of view and external issues point of view are determined under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages.

ABCD analysis framework has been used for analysis of a concept "Higher Education Stage Model". The characteristics of the concept are evaluated based on identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. The result supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique in any concept/idea performance evaluation [22-23]. ABCD analysis framework is also used for analysing National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) accreditation process on higher education institutions [24]. The various features of the NAAC accreditation system is evaluated based on identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of some of the chosen issues like organizational issues, Faculty performance issues, student development / progression issues, social / environmental / community engagement issues, Infrastructure And Learning resources, and Issues on Innovations Creativity and Best Practices. The affecting factors under these issues found out using focus group method and the constituent critical elements under each factor are identified. The result supported the logic of using ABCD analyzing technique in any System/concept performance evaluation. In another paper on "Study on ABCD Analysis Technique for Business Models, business strategies, Operating Concepts & Business Systems", the author discussed the detailed ABCD framework for quantitative studies and explained how this framework can be used for four specific instances namely Business model, Business strategy, Operational concept and Functional system are

outlined here. Finally, ABCD analysing framework is compared with other known analyzing techniques like SWOC, Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) analysis, EFE & IFE Matrices, BCG analysing frameworks, Porter's Five Forces Model, and PESTLE Analysis [13]. Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India is another paper published using this model in which for six determinant issues related to the functioning of a University has been chosen. These are Organizational aspects, Students Progression, Faculty development, Societal & other stakeholders issues, Governance, Leadership, and Issues on Innovations and Best Practices. Four key issues were identified under each of these and critical constituent elements under these factors are worked out. Through this analysis, 192 critical constituent elements which satisfy the success of a private university have been explored [25-26].

Recently, another paper on "Study of New National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) System using ABCD Framework, is published in which the ranking system is evaluated using four constructs Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages, this system consider all determinant issues in key areas through analyzing the major issues and identifying the critical constituent elements and concluded that NIRF provides a comprehensive ranking suitable for higher educational institutions and it takes care of many small and subtle aspects comparable to quality assessment criterion of National Assessment and Accreditation Council. [27]. ABC model recently developed by Aithal P.S & Suresh Kumar P.M. [28], focus on measuring annual research performance of higher educational institutions. According to this model, an organization can calculate its annual research performance using its annual research output by taking into account the following factors such as the number of articles published in refereed journals, the number of books published, and the number of chapters in edited book or number of business cases published in Journals. Studying the implications of a system or model considering all determinants in key areas and analysing the key issues to identify the effective factors and its critical constituent element is the task of ABCD analysis model [29].

The ABCD framework is also used for factor and elemental analysis of the usage of dye-doped polymer films for photonic applications. The various affecting factors under the determinant issues like Material Issues, Application Issues, Commercialization Issues, Production/Service providers Issues, Customer Issues, and Environmental/Social Issues. The constituent critical elements of these factors are listed under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated. The analysis has brought about 204 critical constituent elements which satisfy the success of this analysis methodology [30].

6. ABCD Analysis on Theory A:

6.1. ABCD Listing:

Apart from using ABCD framework for Qualitative analysis, in several research studies, ABCD analysis is limited and simplified to only listing of various advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of either concept, models, systems, strategies, technology, or ideas [31-37]. These studies on ABCD listing can be analysed in detail using ABCD framework either qualitatively or quantitatively for further research. In this section, we have used ABCD analysis for the qualitative listing of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of Theory A.

(1) Advantages:

- ✓ Opportunity to set the objective of organization and dissemination to all employees.
- ✓ Opportunity to set the goal of each employee based on his/her potential.

- ✓ Sets the short term and long term target for individuals and groups.
- ✓ Employees are motivated by creating a working environment and confidence building.
- ✓ Develops a working strategy to ensure winning in the task.
- ✓ The challenge is created through role model performance by the leaders.
- ✓ Boosting the performance through continuous monitoring and guiding.
- ✓ Fixing the accountability changes the lazy, lethargic, and negative mindset.
- ✓ Suited to changes in the employee mindset profile in the new century.
- ✓ Acknowledges human potential and capability to create change.
- ✓ Emphasizes quest for creativity.
- ✓ This style of management raises team spirit to high levels.
- ✓ Individual objective and organizational objective could become one at the same.

(2) Benefits:

- ✓ Employee assumes responsibility utilizing opportunity to perform
- ✓ Accountability results in sustainable organizational effectiveness
- ✓ Utilizing creativity as operational energy
- ✓ Optimum performance by employees coincided both individual and organizational goal.
- ✓ Focussed challenge through role model assures performance and ensures success.
- ✓ Set target and fix accountability ensures creativity and hard work.
- ✓ Continuous monitoring ensures accelerated progress in the task,
- ✓ Changing outlook of the modern workforce.
- ✓ Changing perspectives of employers.
- ✓ Changing the style of management.
- ✓ Democratic expectations of labour unions.
- ✓ Newer forms of governance.

(3) Constraints:

- ✓ Differentiating talents is difficult in complex organisations
- ✓ Not all employees may be proactive in setting targets
- ✓ The strategy to the approach is subject to further test
- ✓ The absence of role model may feed negative thinking in the mind of employees.
- ✓ Setting accountability is difficult based on employee social conditions in the society.
- ✓ Implementing accountability is also difficult in some organizations.
- ✓ There may be hesitation in accepting theory A as a basic philosophy for motivation and management.
- ✓ Not all organizations have strong and committed leadership.
- ✓ Sustainability of results for the long term is a challenge.
- ✓ Some individuals may be pessimistic about their own potential.
- ✓ Jealousy towards role models may hamper positive spirit.

(4) Disadvantages:

- ✓ Takes time to generate output from slow performers
- ✓ Self-exploration needs effort and demands genuineness
- ✓ Inability to realize targets may give frustration
- ✓ Target setting would be a difficult process for some.
- ✓ All employees may not assume responsibility easily.
- ✓ Some individuals fail to be motivated by creativity.
- ✓ Results may be slow in forthcoming.

- ✓ Demands committed leaders as managers and role models.
- ✓ Negative accountability is difficult to accept in the society.

6.2 ABCD Framework Applied to Theory A:

Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a System can be used to analyze and understand the model/system in an effective way. As per this analysis technique [18], the effectiveness of a business model/concept/system can be studied by identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages by considering various determinant issues like organizational objectives, employers and employees perspective, customer/student perspective and environmental/ social perspective as in the block diagram of determinant issues affecting the Theory A and is shown in figure 2 and figure3.

Figure 2: Determinant issues for Factor & Elemental Analysis for Theory 'A'

Figure 3: Block diagram of issues affecting Theory A as per ABCD framework.

As per the ABCD framework [18], the various determinant issues of related to the Theory A for Organizational Performance identified using focus group method are : (1) Organizational Objectives, (2) Employees Issues, (3) Managers Issues, (4) Ideological Issues, (5) Societal and Stake Holder Issues. Each determinant issue has sub-issues called key attributes used for analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages which are the four major constructs of the framework. The factors affecting the various determinant issues of Theory A for each key issue under four constructs are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely, focus group [38-43] and are listed in table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Theory A for Organizational Performance using ABCD framework.

Determinant Issues	Key Issues/ Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Organizational issues	Task	Jointly set	Compliance out of will	Hesitations to participate	Task unfinished
	Relationship	Collaboration	Comradeship	Mistrust	Create distance
	Motivation	Involves every one	Teamwork	Diversity	Affects outcome
	Performance	Role models	Commitment	Acceptability	Difficult to follow
Managerial Issues	Task	Rely on employee potential	Greater efficiency	Weak administration	Limiting managerial role
	Relationship	Coordial relationship	Conducive to creativity	Suspicion	Deviate from focus
	Motivation	Self evaluation	Sustainable	Personal motives	Negative attitude
	Performance	Less supervision	No complaints	Poor skills	Low profile
Employee issues	Task	Expression of creativity	Accountability	Hindrances	Low responsibility
	Relationship	Faith in potential	Builds trust	Undermining capacity	Poor yield
	Motivation	Self generated	Non-financial rewards	Wrong role models	Poor inspiration
	Performance	Meets standards	Recognition	Unset goals	Unmet targets
Ideological Issues	Task	Inspired by organization	Application of knowledge and skills	Inactive organization	Poor result
	Relationship	Newer ways of thinking	More productive employees	Conservative mindset	Stagnation
	Motivation	New models and examples	Results in increased responsibility	Negative thinking	Non-accomplishment
	Performance	Sense of commitment	Increased accountability	Identification with job	Disintegration
Societal & Stakeholders Issues	Task	Newer ways of handling	Task simplified	Readiness to change	Resistance
	Relationship	Harmonious work culture	More productive	Strained society	Disturbed relations
	Motivation	Better working mechanisms	Increased acceptability	Power relations	Changed equations
	Performance	More reliability	Results assured.	Increased skepticism	Progress affected

7. Critical Constituent Elements as per ABCD Model:

The critical constituent elements (CCE) of these factors are listed under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated in tables 3 to 6.

Table 3: Advantages of Theory A for Organizational Performance

S.No	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements (CCE)
1	Organizational issues	Jointly set	Collective planning
			Identification with organization
		Collaboration	Mutuality
		Involves everyone	Understanding
2	Managerial Issues	Rely on employee potential	Defined goal
			Shared goal
		Coordial relationship	Excel in performance
		Self evaluation	Pride in distinguish
3	Employee issues	Expression of creativity	Assumption of capability
			Utilization of capability
		Faith in potential	Trust
		Self generated	Managerial Style
4	Ideological Issues	Inspired by organization	Ability to introspect
			Owning mistakes
		Newer ways of thinking	Self-control
		New models and examples	Self-direction
5	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Newer ways of handling	Nurturing Climate
			Conducive environment
		Harmonious work culture	Demonstrated skill
		Better working mechanisms	Achievement
6	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Inspired by organization	Inherent interest
			Commitment Job
		Newer ways of thinking	Fulfilling requirements
		New models and examples	Sticking to the specification
7	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Inspired by organization	Managerial Leadership
			Organizational culture
		Newer ways of thinking	Open mind
		New models and examples	Creative
8	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Inspired by organization	Star performers
			Desire to follow others
		Newer ways of thinking	Identification with job
		New models and examples	Identification with organization
9	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Newer ways of handling	Changed outlook
			Easiness to accomplish
		Harmonious work culture	Shared values
		Better working mechanisms	Complementary concerns
10	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Newer ways of handling	Organizational feasibility
			Operational viability
		Harmonious work culture	Increased confidence
		Better working mechanisms	Improved output

Table 4: Benefits of Theory A for Organizational Performance

S.No	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements (CCE)
1	Organizational issues	Compliance out of will	More freedom
			More encouragement
		Comradeship	Strong friendship bonds

		Teamwork	Oriented to common goal
			Common identity
		Commitment	Opportunity to develop capability
			Interest in the task
2	Managerial Issues	Greater efficiency	Identification with the organization
			Involvement in fixing target
		Conducive to creativity	Newer style of managing
			Workplace relations
Sustainable	Work based relations		
	Consistency		
No complaints	Realistic		
	Faith in employee		
3	Employee issues	Accountability	Trust in manager
			Responsibility to oneself
		Builds trust	Responsibility to job giver
			Competency
Non-financial rewards	Reliability		
	Better acknowledgement		
4	Ideological Issues	Recognition	Higher life goals
			Individual accomplishment
		Application of knowledge and skills	Collective contribution
			Organizational climate
More productive employees	Changed outlook		
	Required time		
5	Societal & Stakeholder Issues	Results in increased responsibility	Required extent
			Managerial style
		Increased accountability	Employee behaviour
			Extent of commitment
Task simplified	Assuming responsibility		
	System in place		
More productive	Faith in system		
	Conducive environment		
Increased acceptability	Congruent to needs		
	Like change		
Results assured.	Concern for others		
	Time tested		
			Accepted

Table 5: Constraints of Theory A for Organizational Performance

S.No	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements (CCE)
1	Organizational issues	Hesitations to participate	Discrimination
			Disapproval
		Mistrust	Domination
			Negative thinking
Diversity	Knowledge differences		
	Skill differences		
Acceptability	Desire to improve		
	Willingness to change		
2	Managerial Issues	Weak administration	Wrong assumptions
			Poor implementation skills
		Suspicion	Employee-manager gap
Vested interest			
		Personal motives	Bias

			Closed mind
		Poor skills	Wrong selection
			Wrong placement
3	Employee issues	Hindrances	Discouragement
			Wrong supervision
		Undermining capacity	Wrong guess
			Weak human relations
		Wrong role models	Confusion
			Wrong identification
		Unset goals	Slow performers
		Poor clarity	
4	Ideological Issues	Inactive organization	Lacks vision
			Poor leadership
		Conservative mindset	Reactionary attitude
			Lacks of orientation
		Negative thinking	Transparency
			Perspectives
		Identification with job	Misgivings
		Prejudices with employer	
5	Societal & Stakeholders Issues	Readiness to change	Lack of support
			Stereo-typed thinking
		Strained society	Political ideology
			Divided interest
		Power relations	Trade unions
			Employer interests
		Increased skepticism	Diversity
		Differences	

Table 6: Disadvantages of Theory A for Organizational Performance

S.No	Issue	Factors affecting	Critical Constituent Elements (CCE)
1	Organizational issues	Task unfinished	Nature of task
			Time for completion
		Create distance	Differences in perception
			Differences in consumption
		Affects outcome	Reluctant to participate
		Exclusion from involving	
		Difficult to follow	Pessimism
			Wrong conception
2	Managerial Issues	Limiting managerial role	Narrow perspective
			Doubts
		Deviate from focus	Lost professionalism
			Priority changed
		Negative attitude	Unwillingness to take blame
		Afraid of criticism	
		Low profile	Low drive
			Dependence
3	Employee issues	Low responsibility	Loss of identity
			Suppression
		Poor yield	Crush initiative
			Over imposing
		Poor inspiration	Unwillingness to copy
		Unrealistic expectation	
		Unmet targets	Poor judgement
			Lack of clarity
4	Ideological Issues	Poor result	Low focus on efficiency
			Poor work culture

		Stagnation	Indifference
			Lack of concern
		Non-accomplishment	Wrong models
			Reluctance to accept
		Disintegration	Unhealthy competition
			Intentional damage
5	Societal & Stakeholders Issues	Resistance	Unfamiliar with task
			Unpreparedness
		Disturbed relations	Misunderstanding
			Misinformation
		Changed equations	Feud
			Hostility
		Progress affected	Suspicion
			No assurance

8. Advantages of CCE Approach:

- ✓ The various affecting factors of a system, idea, strategy, model, or concept are discussed based on their critical constituent elements under four constructs – Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages.
- ✓ Provides an opportunity for deeper understanding on constituent elements of a system, idea, strategy, model, or concept.
- ✓ Segregating based on ranking of the constituent elements by naming them as critical elements.
- ✓ The framework gives an insight into various affecting factors on predominant key attributes under identified determinant issues leading to critical constituent elements as per CCE approach.

9. Limitations of CCE Approach:

- ✓ There is no rigorous method of identifying CCEs either concept / idea / model / systems / strategy wise or 181 organization-wise. Whatever elements that emerge in the analysis which the researcher may perceive as being critical may not all apply at any one point of time. They serve as probabilities.
- ✓ CCE approach lays more bias on researchers individually rather than on the concept/idea/model/systems/strategy or 181 organization as a whole. Thus, this approach does not provide the base for aggregating individual CCEs into a clear concept/idea/model/systems/strategy or 181 organizational pattern relevant for concept/idea/model/systems/strategy design and deployment.
- ✓ CCE approach is specifically useful for systems, concept, idea, model, and strategy. It assumes that determinant issues are already identified. If that is so, CCE approach is useful otherwise it leaves a vacuum.

10. Conclusion:

The mindset of the modern day employee has undergone enormous change due to changes in technology and means of production, production relations, customer and societal perception and one’s own expectations. The application of ‘Theory A’ for organizational performance is relevant to the management of present day workforce where managerial philosophy is based on changed assumptions. This is a management strategy which believes in delivering targets as responsibility, the feeling of creativity, and contribution for motivation, identifying with the organization as commitment and accountability as a hallmark of efficiency. CCE approach which is followed in ABCD analysis technique of Theory A brings forward the elements which are critical to the success of the new philosophy of management. CCE

approach is a bottom-up strategy which derives critical constituent elements through analysis of determinant issues leading to key issues and then to affecting factors.

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